

MIRRI-ERIC Policy on Intellectual Property Rights

Public investments in research are closely dependent on their contribution to innovation and growth. MIRRI-ERIC fosters the link of research with industry and thus their essential contribution to innovation. The concept of MIRRI-ERIC with its rich services infrastructure and the implementation of the Collaborative Work Environment (MIRRI CWE) with its clusters and programs supports two measures of this important “alliance”: the first is the direct link of science to companies and second an Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Policy allowing the commercialization of collaboration results through individually chosen mechanisms in which MIRRI-ERIC itself has no stake. MIRRI-ERIC as a public Research Infrastructure (RI) provides an ideal platform to facilitate key research affecting public as well as private R&D and innovation and thus is an instrument supporting public research policy as well as government's role in encouraging innovation.

The key elements of the MIRRI-ERIC policy on IPR

The aim of the MIRRI-ERIC IPR policy is that intellectual property rights shall not become an obstacle to the use of data and knowledge from the MIRRI-ERIC RI for innovation and research & development. Securing non-restricted access, supporting freedom of use, identifying proprietary and copyrighted materials and withdrawal from property rights claims resulting from collaboration between partners are the pillars of the MIRRI-ERIC IPR policy:

1. MIRRI-ERIC recognizes and respects the key role of Intellectual Property (IP) assets in driving innovation as well as the importance of fostering a culture of invention through the collaboration between public sector bases science and research with industry.
2. MIRRI-ERIC is aware of the dynamic nature of communication and information technology and that the value of existing IP comes from the ability of its owner to control its use. MIRRI-ERIC will respect this and applicable laws in the creation of the Collaborative Work Environment (MIRRI-ERIC CWE) and the MIRRI-ERIC Information System (MIRRI-IS) at the transfer procedures for data and knowledge.

3. MIRRI-ERIC users will receive according to the [Terms & Conditions](#) a non-restricted access for their scientific, commercial, educational and research-related use of the knowledge, information and data made available by MIRRI-ERIC and not explicitly marked as “confidential”.
4. MIRRI-ERIC as well as its Partners and users acknowledge copyrighted material and intellectual property rights for the purpose of providing and carrying out services, collaborations and matchmaking.
5. The carrying out of the Work Program of MIRRI-ERIC could generate intellectual property. MIRRI-ERIC may claim intellectual property rights within applicable national and international jurisdictions over tools, data, products or any other results developed or generated by MIRRI-ERIC while carrying out the Work Program.
6. In the context of collaborations within MIRRI-ERIC, joint intellectual property between the Partners and users might be generated. The general MIRRI-ERIC policy is that Partners have optimal freedom to generate value out of intellectual property. The exploitation of the intellectual property as a result of collaborative work in MIRRI-ERIC should thus be as flexible as possible and should be negotiated between the Partners on a case-by-case basis. In case of joint inventions between industry and academia the academic partners should benefit in the form of royalties or other benefit-sharing models that properly reflect and reward the contribution of public resources, expertise and work.
7. MIRRI-ERIC encourages Partners and users to define agreements covering the management of intellectual property issues, taking into consideration the specificities of the collaboration and/or project and the relevant participants. These agreements should govern aspects like but not limited to handling and ownership of information, data and/or material, use and dissemination of results, access rights and confidentiality matters.
8. MIRRI-ERIC is aware of the dynamic nature of communication and information technology and that the value of existing IP comes from the ability of its owner to control its use. MIRRI-ERIC will respect this and applicable laws in the creation of the Collaborative Work Environment (MIRRI-ERIC CWE) and the MIRRI-ERIC Information System (MIRRI-ERIC IS) at the transfer procedures for data and knowledge.

9. MIRRI-ERIC users will receive according to the Terms & Conditions a non-restricted access for their scientific, commercial, educational and research-related use of the knowledge, information and data made available by the MIRRI-IS and not explicitly marked as “confidential”.
10. MIRRI-ERIC as well as its partners and users acknowledge copyrighted material and intellectual property rights for the purpose of providing and carrying out services, collaborations and matchmaking.
11. The carrying out of the work program of MIRRI-ERIC could generate intellectual property. MIRRI-ERIC may claim intellectual property rights within applicable national and international juris-dictions over tools, data, products or any other results developed or generated by MIRRI-ERIC while carrying out the work program. This will ensure making the results openly accessible and preventing others from imposing restrictions on MIRRI-ERIC.
12. In the context of collaborations within the MIRRI-ERIC RI, joint intellectual property between MIRRI-ERIC partners and users might be generated. The general MIRRI-ERIC policy is that partners have optimal freedom to generate value out of intellectual property. The exploitation of the intellectual property as a result of collaborative work in MIRRI-ERIC should thus be as flexible as possible and should be negotiated between the partners on a case-by-case basis. In case of joint inventions between industry and academia the academic partners should benefit in the form of royalties or other benefit-sharing models that properly reflect and reward the contribution of public resources, expertise and work.
13. MIRRI-ERIC encourages partners and users to define agreements covering the management of intellectual property issues, taking into consideration the specificities of the collaboration and/or project and the relevant participants. These agreements should govern aspects like but not limited to handling and ownership of information, data and/or material, use and dissemination of results, access rights and confidentiality matters.